

Green Index: A measure of locally available green energy for sustainable, grid-aware data center operations

Orestis Vantzios
IPTO
Athens, Greece
o.vantzios@admie.gr

Dimitrios Skipis
IPTO
Athens, Greece
d.skipis@admie.gr

Efthimia Chassiotti
IPTO
Athens, Greece
ehasiotti@admie.gr

Ioannis Moraitis
IPTO
Athens, Greece
imoraitis@admie.gr

Abstract—In the context of the GLACIATION project, the Greek transmission system operator IPTO is using the project platform to orchestrate the distribution of computational loads among data centers located at a number of distinct sites, with the objective of minimizing the environmental cost. To facilitate this, we introduce the ‘Green Index’, a novel supply-side measure of locally available green energy. The index can be derived directly from a stream of telemetry data, is strongly correlated to CO₂ emissions, and is comparable across different locations and times. Its introduction is an important stepping stone towards sustainable, grid-aware data center operations.

Index Terms—Data center power, Electricity supply industry, Green computing, SCADA systems, Smart grids

I. INTRODUCTION

The GLACIATION project¹ is creating a platform to provide green and secure data operations across the entirety of the edge-to-cloud continuum[1]. To this end, the partners are developing a novel metadata fabric[2] hosted over a flexible architecture for distributed knowledge graphs[3], together with suitable privacy-preserving[4], [5] and energy-conserving[6], [7] modules.

As part of the project, the Greek Independent Power Transmission Operator (IPTO) is tasked with testing the sustainability aspects of the platform. Our tests consider the scenario where three data centers are collocated at three distinct IPTO sites (Fig. 5), with the GLACIATION platform facilitating the exchange of data and computational workloads between them. The objective is to minimize the environmental cost by steering work towards sites with locally available green energy. Being the Transmission System Operator (TSO), we have at our disposal telemetry data from the SCADA² system at the grid substations that provide power to the three sites. The challenge then is to make this information available to the platform orchestrator in such a form that would enable it to schedule the execution of computations whenever and wherever green energy is readily available.

Given the rapidly rising power needs of data centers, expected to reach 35 gigawatts for the US alone by 2030 [8], it is not surprising that a number of metrics for their energy efficiency and environmental impact have been proposed. One

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¹<https://glaciation-project.eu>

²Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition

Figure 1. National power transmission grid of Greece, managed by the Independent Power Transmission Operator (IPTO).

of the most complete sets of such metrics is the collection of GPIs (Green Performance Indicators) of Project GAMES [9]. The GPIs cover all aspects of data center operations and are organized in a hierarchy of layers, starting from individual compute nodes and applications, all the way up to an organization in its entirety.

From our point-of-view as a TSO, all these GPIs are fundamentally *demand-side metrics*. Our use case for GLACIATION brings to focus a particular property of data centers that distinguishes them from other big energy consumers: as part of a cloud, data centers operate in a geographically and temporally dispersed manner. Data and computational workloads are constantly allocated, cached and reallocated over a number of sites, simultaneously driving and following shifting patterns of energy supply and demand in the process [10]. In that sense, the cloud and the power grid are coupled and need to be considered as a whole.

Our contribution is the definition of the Green Index, a *supply-side measure of locally available green energy*. It is a metric that is strongly correlated to CO₂ emissions, can be derived directly from a stream of TSO data, and is comparable across different locations and times by design. With these properties, we see the introduction of the Green Index as a stepping stone towards *grid-aware data operations at scale*.

Figure 2. Schematic of a substation, with connections to the rest of the transmission grid, to local energy producers, and downstream to end consumers via the local distribution (DSO) grid. The Transmission System Operator (TSO) collects telemetry data at each connection.

II. THE GREEN INDEX

A. Transmission grid topology

At the top level, the power transmission grid can be thought off as a network of substations connected to each other via high-voltage (hundreds of KV) transmission lines, see Fig. 1. Locally, such a substation might be connected directly to power generation plants, RES (Renewable Energy Sources), energy storage facilities (typically pumped hydroelectric storage) and big energy consumers such as factories. Downstream, the substation connects to the local DSO (Distribution System Operator) network, which delivers energy to end consumers, domestic and commercial.

At each one of these connections, the TSO constantly collects telemetry data via the SCADA system, see Fig. 2. RTU and PMU (Remote Terminal and Phasor Measurement Unit) sensors generate streams of such data, sampling multiple signals (active and reactive power, phase currents, inter-phase voltage differences) at regular time intervals³. In particular, the TSO continuously monitors at each substation the electrical power flow to and from the rest of the grid.

B. Local power balance

The main insight behind the calculation of the Green Index is that *the net outgoing power flow from a TSO substation to the rest of the grid is equal to the local excess capacity*. This follows from the energy balance equation at the site (for a fixed time):

$$\begin{aligned} P_{in} + P_{local} &= P_{out} + L \\ \Rightarrow P_{net} &:= P_{out} - P_{in} = P_{local} - L \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where P_{in} , P_{out} is the total incoming (negative) and outgoing (positive) power to/from the rest of the transmission grid, P_{local} is the total power from local sources, and L is the total local load. We can see that a large positive net balance on the left-hand side, $P_{net} \gg 0$, implies that the local energy production P_{local} outpaces the local load L (which includes local operation/transmission losses, and energy storage such as pumping). Conversely, $P_{net} \ll 0$ indicates that the site is importing energy from the rest of the grid, to handle local

³Sub-second sampling rates for RTUs, typically 2-10 samples per second. For PMUs, sampling rates vary between once per 10 secs and once per min.

Figure 3. The RES-adjusted power balance R combines information about the local power balance P_{net} in/out of a substation, together with the ratio r_{RES} of renewable sources in the national energy mix.

Figure 4. Normalization of a quantity $R(t)$ via its signed percentile rank $I(t;W)$. The magnitude of I is the fraction of measurements within a preceding window W (in the plot $W = 14$) that have values between 0 and $R(t)$, and it has the same sign with $R(t)$. It takes values in $[-1, 1]$.

loads outpacing local energy production. For convenience, we introduce P_{exp} , P_{imp} , the net imported/exported power, which are the positive and negative parts of P_{net} respectively:

$$P_{net} = P_{exp} - P_{imp}, \quad P_{exp} \geq 0 \text{ and } P_{imp} \geq 0. \quad (2)$$

From a sustainability point of view, it makes sense to handle workloads preferentially during times when $P_{net} > 0 \Rightarrow P_{exp} > 0$, and to try and defer work when $P_{net} < 0 \Rightarrow P_{imp} > 0$. We reinforce this by incorporating r_{RES} , the ratio of renewable sources in the national energy mix (see the Appendix), into our calculation⁴. We introduce the RES-adjusted power balance:

$$R := r_{RES}P_{exp} - (1 - r_{RES})P_{imp}. \quad (3)$$

Using R as a measure, spare local capacity at times of high national RES production scores high ($R \gg 0$), whereas importing energy at times of high national consumption of non-renewable energy scores low ($R \ll 0$), see Fig. 3.

C. The Index

The adjusted power balance R is informative of the availability of renewable energy at each location at a given time, but it can not be readily used to draw comparisons

⁴We take an agnostic stance with regards to whether P_{local} comes from renewable sources or not. This is both difficult to evaluate in practice, and non-trivial to define precisely. We opt to use instead the national energy mix, which is reported directly by the TSO and does not involve any further assumptions about the operation of the grid.

Figure 5. Topology of our SCADA dataset. Each arrow corresponds to a high-voltage transmission line between substations and a corresponding set of telemetry signals. The power balance P_{net} at each site is calculated as an algebraic sum over the connections.

between locations. To this end, we *normalize* it by comparing $R(t)$ against all the values inside a suitable window W . We consider a 1-week interval ending in t , which is long enough to cover day/night and workday/weekend variations in consumption, as well as variations in RES output due to the weather. Taking the signed percentile rank over W :

$$I(t; W) := \begin{cases} P(0 < R(s) \leq R(t) \mid s \in W), & R(t) > 0 \\ 0, & R(t) = 0 \\ -P(0 > R(s) \geq R(t) \mid s \in W), & R(t) < 0 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

we get an index between -1 and 1, see Fig. 4, that is monotone as a function of $R(t)$ and respects its sign.

Finally, we arrive at the Green Index by rescaling to fit the value range $[0, 1]$:

$$I_{green}(t; W) := \frac{1 + I(t; W)}{2} \in [0, 1]. \quad (5)$$

Green Index values at a given site and time:

- $I_{green} < 0.5$ means net power import,
- $I_{green} > 0.5$ means net power export,
- $I_{green} \approx 0$ means net imports of non-renewable energy close to a 1-week maximum,
- $I_{green} \approx 1$ means local spare/national RES capacity close to a 1-week maximum.

III. RESULTS

We implemented the calculation of the Green Index described above using Polars, a data processing library written in Rust. Polars' *lazy evaluation*, i.e. the ability to build and execute entire pipelines without the need to load the entirety of the required datasets in memory first, has been crucial in handling the amount of data involved.

Our SCADA dataset covers three IPTO substations connected to each other and to the rest of the transmission grid, see Fig. 5 for a sketch of the topology. Examining the derived Green Index over the span of a year (Fig. 6), we notice that two of the sites ('B' and 'C') are net importers of energy, with $I_{green} < 0.5$ year-long, whereas site 'A' is connected to local power sources and is often a net energy exporter with $I_{green} > 0.5$. Looking at the daily trend (Fig. 7), we notice that the index at sites 'B' and 'C' is highly correlated, with the index at site 'C' showing less intraday variation. Comparing across the four quarters, we also notice strong seasonal variations, particularly in r_{RES} as expected due to shifting availability of wind and solar energy.

Figure 6. A single year of the Green Index for the three sites and the RES ratio. Daily average (solid line) with intraday 90% percentile intervals (shaded area).

Figure 7. Daily variation of the Green Index for the three sites (A blue, B orange, C green) and the RES ratio (dashed red line); hourly values averaged over the four quarters of a single year.

The correlation between RES availability and the Green Index is more clearly pictured in Fig. 8, where we plotted the CO₂ emission rate (estimated on a national level, see the Appendix) vs the best (max) Green Index available across all three sites at any given time. We note a drop in the emission rate from 400 kgr/MWh down to 200 kgr/MWh as the index increases from 0.5 to 0.8, in support of our use of it as a signal for orchestrating computational work.

IV. OUTLOOK

Having established the Green Index as a means to distribute computational workloads across space and time in an environmentally conscious manner, we now turn our attention to future work.

A promising direction is to scale the Green Index dataset up. This can be achieved by covering more TSO sites, while at the same time incorporating a more refined RES dataset. Whereas in the present work we use the energy mix on the national level, it would be meaningful to go down to the regional level (NUTS 2-3[11]) and to take into account local patterns in energy production and consumption.

Figure 8. Correlation of CO₂ emission rate (in kgr/MWh, calculated based on the national energy mix, see the Appendix) vs the best (max) available Green Index among the sites. The emission rate drops from around 400 kgr/MWh at $I_{green} \approx 0.5$ down to 200 kgr/MWh at $I_{green} \approx 0.8$.

A larger dataset can also be combined with the development of an ML model for the short-term prediction of the Green Index. We got good preliminary results on our current dataset by fine-tuning the last (linear) layer of a MOMENT model, part of a family of open time-series foundation models [12].

Another dimension we aim to explore is that of other objectives beyond sustainability. As a TSO, we are acutely aware of the impact data centers have on the power grid, with phenomena such as grid instability and grid congestion observed with increasing frequency and severity. The introduction of corresponding indices, analogous to the Green Index, would be an important step towards closing the grid-cloud loop, incentivizing grid-aware and grid-responsible data center operations.

APPENDIX

IPTO provides daily reports of the mix of energy sources in the national power supply. These are publicly available through IPTO’s File Download API⁵. A suitable API call⁶ yields a JSON file that includes a link to an Excel spreadsheet.

The linked Excel file contains an hour-by-hour breakdown of various loads, imports/exports and power sources (Table I). We derive from these the desired ratio r_{RES} using the formula⁷:

$$r_{RES} := \frac{E_{RES} + E_{hydro}}{L + \max(T, 0)},$$

where E_{RES} is ‘TOTAL RES’, E_{hydro} is ‘TOTAL HYDRO’, L is ‘Συνολικό Φορτίο’ (‘Total Load’) and T is ‘EXPORTS-IMPORTS’. Note that applying this formula over the entire day reproduces exactly the daily RES ratio reported by IPTO via the API and the IPTO app.

The same Excel file also includes an hour-by-hour breakdown of the energy generated per source type. We can derive

⁵<https://www.admie.gr/agora/statistika-agoras/file-download-api>

⁶<https://www.admie.gr/getOperationMarketFile?dateStart=YYYY-MM-DD&dateEnd=YYYY-MM-DD&FileCategory=SystemRealizationSCADA>, where ‘YYYY-MM-DD’ is the desired date.

⁷A more precise symbol for this quantity might indeed be r_{zero} , since it is in fact the ratio of zero carbon emission sources in the energy mix.

Table I
SYSTEMREALIZATIONSCADA SPREADSHEET

Row Header	Values in MWh, per hour				
‘Hours’	01	02	...	23	24
‘Συνολικό Φορτίο’	Total load (inc. storage)				
‘EXPORTS-IMPORTS’	Interconnections balance				
‘TOTAL RES’	Total energy from renewables				
‘TOTAL HYDRO’	Total hydroelectric energy				

Table II
CO₂ EMISSIONS

Energy source	CO ₂ emission rate
RES (solar, wind)	0 kgr/MWh
Hydroelectric	0 kgr/MWh
Natural gas	387.40 kgr/MWh
Lignite	1382.64 kgr/MWh

the hourly CO₂ emissions rate (in kgr/MWh) on the national level, using the information in Table II.

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